

The Contextual Critical Thinking Coding Manual (CCTCM) – the complete coding manual

This is the complete set of the CCTCM. It is composed of two main parts: the first, the Contextual Profile (CP) – focusing on the topics and subtopics discussed by students in a physical chemistry laboratory context, and the second, the Critical Thinking Skills and Subskills Profile (CTSP) - the operationalized critical thinking (CT) core skills and subskills with related examples which captures elements of CT in practice based on the verbal interactions of the participants.

Each part can be used independently, combined, or serve a different purpose. However, when combined, one needs to use the CP part first and follow with the CTSP part.

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Part I - The Contextual Profile (CP) - Determining the topics that are discussed inside the laboratory

1. Introduction – uses and structure of the coding manual

1.1. The aim

This coding manual aims to code each coding unit (see section 1.3 for definition) to determine the main topic or focus of the unit.

1.2. Where it applies – the transcripts:

For coding, the source of the Coding Units is the transcripts of the conversation recorded while the students were working (in pairs) in the laboratory. Their conversation was recorded through video and audio records to capture the oral speech (with the audio device) and provide additional information (with the video records) that is not audible, but is necessary for understanding what the content of the oral speech was referring to.

Example 1.2.1: “Would you like to work on this?”. In this statement, the audible information is insufficient to understand what the speaker refers to. From the video records, the information about what “this” refers to will be provided in the transcript. In such a case, the supporting information will be: [student 1 was pointing at the spectrophotometer] or [student 2 was pointing to the script].

The transcripts focused on the content related to the work done inside the laboratory; other contexts, such as social talk, talk about different courses, content unrelated to chemistry, etc., were excluded from the transcribing process. Instead of such statements, a short indication of the content is noted in [].

Example 1.2.2: [social talk]

The transcripts indicate whether the speaker is the students working in pairs/triplets by indicating Stu1, Stu2, and Stu3 consistently, students from another group, the laboratory assistants, and the laboratory supervisors.

1.3. Step one - Determination of a coding unit

This coding manual focuses on determining the topics central to each statement. This section will allow the determination of the CUs by providing the definitions and operational aspects.

Determination of the CU:

If the statement has a sentence or question structure, then the CU ends after the meaning of the unit is determined. CU has a distinct meaning; hence, an entity of meaning is described when the statement has a distinct and independent meaning for understanding the transcript's context. The statement can be composed of one or up to as many words as needed to present a unit with independent and distinct meaning.

This means that the CU ends if, and only if, a new main or subordinate clause starts, which has no reference to the previous clause to understand the meaning of the clause. Consequently, the statements *should be broken down into individual CU* when each CU forms an independent context of meaning.

Example 1.3.1: “We need to mix the acid with the base.” – This is a statement that forms an entity of meaning on its own, and therefore, *one CU*.

Example 1.3.2: "wash the tools and in the meanwhile I am working on the calibration phase." – This statement has **two CUs** with two independent meanings:

CU 1: "Wash the tools."

CU 2: "In the meantime, I am working on the calibration phase."

Example 1.3.3: "Do you think our sample is contaminated and we need to make another one?" - This whole statement is **one CU**, since the second main clause "we need to make another one" cannot be understood without the first main clause.

Some statements that form an independent unit do not form a clear meaning; however, it was a **follow-up** on the previous talk. To determine the meaning, the coder has to review **one CU up and/or down** until the context is understood.

Example 1.3.4: "Does this make sense?" – The word "this" has to be understood to determine what this statement refers to. If no supporting information, mentioned in [], is available, then reviewing one **CU up and/or down** is needed for this clarification.

Some statements are a response to the previous talk. If the statement is a relatively **short answer/response** to the previous talk, it is considered a CU in this coding manual.

Example 1.3.5: "Aha, I understand" – this is one CU responding to a previous CU.

Example 1.3.6: "Ok, I will do that" – This CU responds to a previous statement.

Please note that if a CU is a short answer, it automatically receives the subcode (in the short answer category) identical to the code that the previous CU, which it is referring to, received.

So far, we have reviewed several examples and cases of CU that form entities of meaning. However, not all units/statements in the transcripts form an entity of meaning, for they were, for instance, interrupted, lacking clarity due to audio technicalities, or simply because the speaker did not complete the phrase. These CU, although with an incomplete meaning, are necessary for the coding, for they are important for the data analysis process and the drawn conclusions. See category 0 CU with incomplete meaning.

Due to the limitations of the devices used to record the speech and to capture students' activities in the laboratory, the meaning of some statements of the CU cannot be determined. The reasons could include static noises, students being further away from the audio/video device, background noises, etc. In such cases, the CU is considered **inaudible**.

Example 1.3.7: "I think that I should....." [Transcript stops here] – There is no clear idea of the purpose of this sentence since it was incomplete.

Example 1.3.8: "You should put [noise]" – there were technical issues with the audio records, and the rest of the sentence was not recorded or could not be transcribed

Example 1.3.9: "I will start with [high background noises]". This statement was on a specific topic, yet the issue here was the quality of the audio recording. The topic of the statement could not be determined due to audio issues.

Due to the nature of the working environment in the laboratory, working with others, and due to the nature of oral speech, some statements might be interrupted and not completed to form an independent meaning. If the next CU is a continuation of the interrupted CU, then both parts will be considered one CU – even if the speaker was a different person.

Example 1.3.10: Stu1: “I will do, uhmmm, ...”
Stu2: “The calibration” – both statements for one CU.

If the statement was interrupted and the following CU (one CU down) does not complete the interrupted CU, then in this case, the interrupted statement will be considered as an *interrupted speech*.

Example 1.3.11: “Did you know that [Student was interrupted by the laboratory assistant]. In this example, the statement was not completed due to an interruption of speech.

1.4. Speaker-related coding

This coding manual is focused broadly on the topics that students pose and elaborates less on the topics posed by the teaching staff (TS). For this, a distinction between the speakers is made. Most categories are dedicated to students as speakers (all categories except category 9), and specific categories are dedicated to TS as speakers (Categories 0 and 9). TS could be an instructor, laboratory assistant, laboratory supervisor, professor, etc.

2. The Codes of CP – Main Categories, sub-codes, definition, uses and examples

Main Category 0: CU with incomplete meaning

Sub category (specific topic)		Code Label	Definition	When to use the code	When NOT to use the code and <i>Alternative codes</i>	Examples of where the code applies
0.1 Interrupted speech	0.1.1 Interrupted speech – spoken by a student	BS_S	Sentence / part of a sentence that does not yield a meaning. The sentence is incomplete. For example, it was interrupted by another person, event or that the speaker has stopped speaking for an evident or unevident reason.	The speaker is a student and the CU is an incomplete statement.	The CU has a meaningful context and topic is conceivable.	I think that I should..... [transcripts stops here] The problem here is that..... [transcripts stops here]
	0.1.2 Interrupted speech - spoken by a TS	BS_I		The speaker is a TS and the CU is an incomplete statement.		

Sub category (specific topic)		Code Label	Definition	When to use the code	When NOT to use the code and <i>Alternative codes</i>	Examples of where the code applies
0.2. Inaudible	0.2.1 Inaudible content - spoken by a student	UC_S	Content is undetectable due to audio issues. Usually, the transcript indicates missing information that is due to audio issues (such as scratching or noises that did not enable full transcription of the statement). Occurrence of audio issues prevents the determination of the topic of the CU.	The speaker is a student and the CU is missing information due to audio issues.	The CU has a meaningful context. [noise] [inaudible]
	0.2.2 Inaudible content - spoken by TS	UC_I		The speaker is an instructor and the CU is missing information due to audio issues.		

Main Category 1: Chemical terms and content

Sub category (specific topic)	Code Label	Definition	When to use the code	When NOT to use the code and <i>Alternative codes</i>	Examples of where the code applies
1.1 General Chemistry	CC_G	The TP mentions, explains or asks about chemical terms, principles and general methods, or the alike, but not related to the experiment at hand.	First, check the topic of the experiment, the substances, reactions and all relevant chemical terms, methods and principles from the laboratory manual and/or the necessary prior knowledge. Use this code if the CU refer to any chemical content such as substances, reactions or other chemical terms and principles that are not from the laboratory manual and/or related directly to the experiment (such as referring to the “prior knowledge” section of the laboratory manual).	The CU does not refer to chemical content. <i>However</i> , if the CU refers to chemical content that is directly related to the laboratory manual then consider “Background & Theoretical Chemistry” code.	Did you know that mixing [substance x] with [substance y] can explode? Do you know how oil is refined? Extracting [substance] from [mixture] can be done by [method]
1.2 Background & Theoretical Chemistry	CC_T	The TP talks about, explains or asks for chemical terms principles, and methods or the alike, which is/are related to the experiment.	First, check the topic of the experiment, the substances, reactions and all relevant chemical terms, methods and principles from the laboratory manual and/or the necessary prior knowledge. Use this code if the CU refers to them directly. Here, the content of the CU could refer to the theoretical content as mentioned in the laboratory manual or in other sources (such as: other courses, lectures, textbooks, references etc.).	If the CU does not refer to any of the topics, the substances, reactions or other relevant chemical terms, methods and principles from the laboratory manual. <i>However</i> , if the CU is related to chemical terms in general, then consider “1.1 General Chemistry” code above. All other content that is not theoretical and in general (see provided examples) should be coded in the rest of the codes that belong to other main categories.	What is the chemical structure of [substance]? [substance] can interact with ... Spectrophotometry works on the principle of
1.3 Predicting outcomes and Generating hypotheses	CC_H	The talk about chemical terms and theoretical chemical content for the purpose of creating assumptions, hypothesis or predictions. This generally occurs prior to executing the	The talk refers to establishing and discussing potential relationships between several compounds, theoretical models, mechanisms, etc., together or any combination between them	No (partial or complete) hypotheses, assumption or prediction evolved around chemical terms and content prior to the execution	If I mix [substance x] with [substance y], will it explode? I think that using colometry will not work on this substance

		whole- or parts of the experiment.	prior to executing the whole or sections in the experiment.		
1.4 Generating chemical explanation or expectation – post hoc		The talk about chemical terms and theoretical chemical content for the purpose of establishing an explanation, a connection between substances, principles, and/or models. This generally occurs after to executing the whole- or parts of the experiment and making this explanation/connection is retrospectively.	The talk refers to establishing and discussing potential relationships between several compounds, theoretical models, mechanisms, etc., together or any combination between them after conducting the whole or parts of the experiment. This can be while observing, collecting data and/or after finishing the data collection. This <i>usually</i> follows 4.2 data evaluation or 5.2 process evaluation codes.	No (partial or complete) explanation or connection evolved around chemical terms and content after the execution.	Using higher concentration of acid will speed up the reaction. Light intensity can influence this [light reactive compound] The mathematical equation shows that when absorption is minimum, the emission is maximum
1.5 Theoretical Chemistry - Other		The CU is about chemical terms and theoretical chemical content but in none of the previous subcodes.	The CU is about chemical terms and theoretical chemical content but in none of the previous subcodes.	The CU is not about chemical terms and theoretical chemical content and in none of the previous subcodes.	Radioactive materials are my favorite

Main category 2: Laboratory equipment, substances, and tools (non-digital equipment and tools)

Sub category (specific topic)	Code Label	Definition	When to use the code	When NOT to use the code and <i>Alternative codes</i>	Examples of where the code applies
2.1 Identification and Characteristics	ES_I	The TP talks about laboratory tools, equipment (non-digital, such as glassware), objects and chemical substances that are part of a laboratory and/or of the experiment at hand. The talk is for identifying purposes or related to the characteristics of the objects, equipment, or substances.	The TP is simply mentioning a piece of equipment, substance, or other related tool/object for the purpose of identifying it, indicating, or highlighting features. The talk here is also related to distinguishing a tool from the rest of the options.	If the CU does not refer to any equipment/object/substance. <i>However</i> , If the TP is mentioning an equipment, substance, or other related tool/object for the purpose of further clarifying on how to operate or place in the procedural context of the experiment consider code “2.2 Configuring the equipment”.	Is this the cuvette? I will use this stirrer (but not that tool) The colour is weird Where are beakers that we need? Is this beaker the right one? Where is the iodine Which one is the
2.2 Configuring the Equipment	ES_C	The TP discusses ways to operate the equipment. This can be through asking for- or	If the TP is discussing, instructing, clarifying, or explaining ways to operate an equipment. The discussion,	The CU is not related to the equipment for the purpose of discussing, instructing,	Do we need to tilt this burette Do we take the solution using a pipette? How to make it drip?

		providing- instructions, clarifications, and explanation.	instruction, clarification or explanation could be in the spoken form, by demonstration, pointing towards an object or in combination.	clarifying, or explaining ways to operation.	I think we need to turn this half way, so it doesn't drip too fast Do we need to close the lid How to read the meniscus in this tube Do we count these drops on the wall of the beaker with the total volume?
2.3 Predicting outcomes Generating Hypotheses	ES_H	The talk about equipment and tools for the purpose of creating assumptions or hypothesis regarding their predictions/outcomes. This could occur prior to executing the whole- or parts of the experiment or after the execution.	The talk refers to establishing and discussing potential relationships between the tools/equipment and the experiment and/or outcomes.	No (partial or complete) hypotheses, assumption or prediction evolved around laboratory equipment, substances and/or tools.	What might happen if we do not wash the tools? Using the beaker instead of that one would cause... Leaving the Iodine solution on the table will change the color of the solution
2.4 Equipment – Other	ES_O	The equipment is mentioned but not for the purpose of identifying it, indicating, or highlighting features or to discussing, instructing, or clarifying ways to operate it or to establish hypothesis and predictions and when the context is not related to the experiment at hand.	None of the previous three codes in this category applies, but the content is related to the equipment/tools/substance.	The content of the CU is not related in any way to equipment/tool/substances.	I can use the Erlenmeyer to mix my cocktails

Main category 3: Computers and digital devices (devices and software oriented)

Sub category (specific topic)	Code Label	Definition	When to use the code	When NOT to use the code and <i>Alternative codes</i>	Examples of where the code applies
3.1 Computerized and digital devices and software	CD_I	The simple operational actions (for declarative/informative purposes). Operations related to the digital devices/computers/software (simply, the activities that they perform). This is usually during the operation of such digital devices/computers/software.	The CU is related to the actual operations of the computerized software and digital devices. This is during the operation on the digital devices/computers/software (see examples), and these statements are only for informing about what they are doing/what they should do. The CU is usually a	The talk is not about actions during the operation of digital devices/computers/software. <i>However</i> , if it is related but is more than just declaring actions consider the following codes in this main-category.	Press save Open file Open the spectra I am working of the software

			short informative statement and/or in a command format.		
3.2 Configuration of Computerized and digital devices and software	CD_C	The talk is related to how to set up/operate the digital devices/computers/software.	The CU is concerned with discussing, instructing, or clarifying ways to operate the digital devices/computers/software.	The CU is not about how to operate the digital devices/computers/software.	Where do we put the cuvette How do we save our data How do we start recording How do we turn it on We save the data by ...
3.3 Predicting outcome Generating hypotheses	CD_H	The talk about the digital devices/computers/software for the purpose of creating assumptions, hypothesis or predictions. This could occur prior to executing the whole- or parts of the experiment or after the execution.	The talk refers to establishing and discussing potential relationships between digital devices/computers/software and the experiment.	No (partial or complete) hypotheses, assumption or prediction evolved around the use of the digital devices/computers/software and the experiment.	The light of the spectrophotometer effects the stability of the compound
3.4 Computerized and digital devices and software - other	CD_O	The digital device/computer/software is mentioned but not related to the experiment at hand.	None of the previous codes in this category applies, but is related to the digital devices/computers/software.	The CU is not related in any way to the digital devices/computers/software.	This software reminds me of the other experiment The device is similar to the radar system

Main category 4: Data (value-oriented)*

Sub category (specific topic)	Code Label	Definition	When to use the code	When NOT to use the code and <i>Alternative codes</i>	Examples of where the code applies
4.1 Reading measurements and data	D_I	Event that is part of the experiment. The TP reads aloud data during the experiment.	The content refers to the data, as a value. Could be in a declarative form or confirming form.	The CU refers to data but is beyond the observed value, in such cases, consider the following codes in this category.	Record the value 0.2 Did you say 5.5? Did you record it?
4.2. Evaluating data (cognitive and metacognitive)	D_E	The TP refers to an already recorded data or noted formula. The TP evaluates the obtained data after making the measurement. Here it's about reflecting on the value, do simple mathematical calculations with the data.	The talk refers to an already recorded data in terms of reflecting on and thinking about the meaning and/or accuracy of the value they obtained. Such as a value being too far from the other measurements. Also, the code here should also be used on processing the values, such	The content of the CU is not concerned with reflection on the obtained data or do simple calculation with it. <i>However</i> , if the content is about attributing the inaccuracy/oddness of the value is due to a failure, inaccuracy, contamination or other external	Look at this spectra The data looks strange/weird This data doesn't look right This is the maximum Do we need to retake this measurement? Do you think the value of [number] makes sense Does this value look normal?

			as normalization, mathematical calculation of errors, etc.	matters that are related to the sampling (data collection process) that could have influenced the value then in this case, consider the code “Evaluating process” in the following category. <i>Also</i> , if the CU is concerned with the actual explanations, underpinning expectations and interpretation on data (with or without evidence or reference) then consider the codes 4.4.1-4.4. “Interpretation, analysis and prediction of data” below.	Do we need to repeat this measurement? The calculation of the errors should be calculated like this...
4.3 Predicting outcomes and Generating hypotheses – prior to execution	D_H	The talk about the data for the purpose of creating assumptions, hypothesis or predictions. This generally occurs prior to executing the whole- or parts of the experiment.	The talk refers to establishing and discussing potential relationships prediction of the values, patterns and alike.	No (partial or complete) hypotheses, assumption or prediction evolved around the (potential) data.	I think we might get here two peaks The data will be in ascending pattern How will the data look like?
4.4.1 Interpretation, predictions and analysis of data - post hoc (without supporting information)	D_A	Statements that are concerned with underpinning expectations from the data, possible explanations, assigning meaning, considering sources of bias and determining the conclusions, significance and implications of the findings. This includes estimating the values of unknown parameters and testing of hypotheses for drawing inferences. These statements do not refer explicitly to supporting information of any kind (meaning, there is no mentioning of evidence, reference or information to support the claim). Usually, this code follows the data evaluation (4.2) code.	The talk refers to discussing data, confronting the obtained data with underpinning expectations and giving meaning to the data, Statements related to expectations from the data (how did they expect the data to look like) after executing the experiment. In some cases, such CU includes words: should, could, must, generally, according to, etc.	When the CU is not related to interpretation of data, confronting underpinning expectations from data drawing conclusion. <i>However</i> , if the CU is related to interpretation, analysis or underpinning prediction but with basis to the claim, then there is a need to indicate the source of the supporting information. For this, consider the following codes 4.4.2-4.4..	The number should be higher here I expected the time to be shorter for this part The data is supposed to look like this,

4.4.2 Interpretation, analysis and prediction of data - post hoc - with supporting information that focus on bias and sampling procedures	D_A_S	Similar to the definition of 4.4.1 and the focus of the explanation relies on the possible factors that may have led to the result and sources of bias such as sampling procedures, margins of error, confidence intervals or other similar factors.	The talks about the data refers to discussing and presenting possible factors that may have led to the discussed result by focusing of the measurement process and inaccuracy of tools/devices.	The basis of the claim is not related to the measurement process and accuracy of tools/devices.	We got a higher value because we did not clean the cuvette well. We got this number maybe because we used the wrong cuvette
4.4.3 interpretation, analysis and prediction of data - post hoc - with supporting information that focus on Theory and chemical proprieties of the compounds	D_A_CC	Similar to the definition of 4.4.1 and the focus of the explanation relies on underpinning predictions and expectations from results based on prior knowledge of theory and chemical proprieties of the compounds.	The talk about the data refers to chemical content knowledge to support the claim.	When the talk does not refer to chemical content knowledge to support the claim.	This material is light sensitive, it does not make sense that it reacts here. We have odd values because this compound decomposes with time We can't see this value because we uses a solvent that dissolves this material
4.4.4 interpretation, analysis and prediction of data - post hoc - with supporting information to the claim based on Chemical principles, kinetics and Mathematical considerations	D_A_CP	Similar to the definition of 4.4.1 and the focus of the explanation relies on underpinning predictions and expectations from results based on prior knowledge of chemical principles, kinetics and mathematical considerations.	The talk about the data refers to chemical principles, theories and laws such as speed of reaction, the law of conservation, mathematical formulas of variables, or other principles to support the claim. When the expectation is based on chemical principles (e.g. laws of kinetics) and mathematical considerations (e.g. changing a value in a mathematical equation).	The talk does not base the claim on chemical principles, theories and laws.	The higher the concentration the faster the reaction is – it is basic kinetics I expect that the higher the concentration of H ⁺ the fastest the reaction should be if we put higher value of absorbance into the formula we should be getting higher value for time
4.4.5 interpretation, analysis and prediction of data - post hoc - with supporting information to the claim based on previously self-obtained data	D_A_PD	Similar to the definition of 4.4.1 and the focus of the explanation relies on conclusions from previously self-obtained data (data that was collected by the students during the day in previous parts of the experiment at hand, such as same steps but with different concentration).	The claim about the data is based on conclusions about data they obtain themselves in the lab, such as comparing to previous results from repetitions or previous part, e.g. part with lower/higher concentration etc.	The claim is not based on conclusions about self-obtained data.	This is taking longer than the measurement with less concentration If this step took 5 minutes, this will take 10 minutes
4.4.6 interpretation, analysis and prediction of data - post hoc - with supporting information to the claim based on	D_A_R	Similar to the definition of 4.4.1 and the focus of the claim is based on information from other reports or data obtained by others.	When the claim about the is based explicitly on information from previous reports.	The claim is not based on information from other reports.	I saw reports from other students, the data does not look similar

information from other reports and other students					
4.4.7 interpretation, analysis and prediction of data - post hoc - with supporting information to the claim based on TS	D_A_TS	Similar to the definition of 4.4.1 and the focus of the claim is based on information from the TS (statements said by the teaching staff).	When the claim about the data is based on information from the TS.	The claim is not based on information from the TS.	The lab supervisor says this value is way too high
4.4.8 interpretation, analysis and prediction of data - post hoc - with supporting information to the claim based on other sources of information	D_A_O	Similar to the definition of 4.4.1 and the focus of the claim is based on information other reasons that were not specified in previous codes.	The claim about the data is related to data interpretation, analysis or predictions but none of the codes 4.4.1-4.4.7 suites.	The CU is not related to data interpretation, analysis or predictions.	This data is not consistent with the way the professor described his research
4.5 Conclusions and next steps (tactical decisions)	D_Con	The CU is concerned with drawing conclusions regarding the obtained data, such as whether to accept/reject the values and as a result outline the next steps that should be taken (for example repeating the measurement, leaving it as it is, etc.).	The CU is about acceptance/rejection of data and the next steps with this decision.	The talk is not concerned with accepting, rejecting, and/or next sept with the data (conclusions) about the data.	I believe that this data is fine after all We will need to make this measurement again We have to go consult the TS about this data
4.6 Data – other	D_O	Referring to the values but is not concerned with the experiment or any modifications related to the experiment.	Mentioning or referring to the values without connection to the experiments, considering inaccuracy/errors or analysis/meaning of the values.	The talk is not related to values they obtained during their measurements and execution of the experiment.	I always get 5, it's my lucky number It's nice to if we get and ascending set of values The graph looks like a tilted infinity

Main category 5: Procedure (process-oriented) **

Sub category (specific topic)	Code Label	Definition	When to use the code	When NOT to use the code and <i>Alternative codes</i>	Examples of where the code applies
5.1.1 Script	P_I_S	The conversation is related to the script. The CU has to explicitly refer to the script in its content or by the supporting information provided in the transcript (see example 1.2.1 in	When simply restating steps from the laboratory manual or rephrasing for the purpose of informing their partners about the needed step(s) and confirming the needed steps.	The talk is not concerned with the steps of the experiment as shown in the script.	[According to the script] We should do the following things... [According to the script] Now we need three beakers, one stirrer and

		the introduction on the coding manual). They talk about the script, by referring to, pointing out information or instructions from the script. Briefing about the steps to do from the script. Usually this conversation occurs after having viewed the script.	Referring to or actively reading from the script should be explicit by either the content of the CU or by the supporting information provided in the transcript.		
5.1.2 Process information (Simply mentioning an overall operation)	P_I	Informative/declarative talk about what the TP is doing. This refers to an overall process that they need to perform, such as titration, calibration, etc.	Mentioning a phase, sub step or an operation that is part of the experiment, for the informative purposes. Usually, this talk is prior to or during the execution, or retrospectively. The talk is for informative purposes about where they are in the procedures.	If the steps are mentioned not for the declarative and conformational purposes only. <i>However</i> , when the talk about a step/operation extends the informative purposes to include an instructional or reflective aspects consider the following four codes in the current category.	We are performing the titration Did you perform the titration phase?
5.2.1 Process Demonstration and instruction	P_D	The TP talks about how to execute a task , they demonstrate how to do a step/phase for the experiment. Give an instruction about how to do a task. This is related to the execution of the steps mentioned in the Laboratory manual or other steps necessary for setting the experiments and collecting data. Note: If the content is specific and/or focused on a tool or hardware/software then is should be coded in other codes (e.g. codes from category 2 and 3).	Mentioning a phase, sub-step or an operation that is part of the experiment, for the purpose of demonstration, explanation or clarification on how the process needs to be carried out.	The process is discussed for its accuracy or any need for adjustments (in such case, consider the next code, Process Evaluation).	We have to put [substance x] in [tool y] and do this to obtain the data. How many times do we do this step? Calibration has to be done like this. How do we measure errors?
5.2.2 Process Evaluating (cognitive and metacognitive)	P_E	This is not mainly concerned with evaluating the data. This is related to the entire process that they executed. The TP evaluates the process in which they obtained data after making the measurement. This can be related to assurance of the measurements that include	The content is concerned with the process and the necessary step needed to insure quality and accuracy. These considerations could be at the beginning of the experiment as a whole or part of the experiment before carrying out the experiment, while setting up	The content is not in a cognitive or metacognitive mode regarding the process. <i>However</i> , if the concern is merely about the value/data – then consider the code “Evaluating Data”.	Did we do the steps right? Do you think that the level of noise/light could have affected our experiments? Do you think our sample is contaminated and we need to make another one? Did we wash the tools well?

		monitoring of the process that was carried out. This has to do with modifying the steps they carried out in the process of obtaining data.	the tools and/or after/during obtaining the data and rethinking the steps they followed. The talk is concerned with adjustments and improvements of a step in the process. The concern could be related to attributing inaccuracy/oddness of the data due to a failure, inaccuracy, contamination or other external matters that are related the process/steps they executed. Might succeed the code “data evaluation”.		This time, we need to do the calibration while making sure that all our tools are washed and dried
5.3 Predicting outcome Generating hypotheses	P_H	The talk about the process for the purpose of creating assumptions, hypothesis or predictions. This generally occurs prior to executing the whole- or parts of the experiment.	The talk refers to establishing and discussing potential relationships and prediction of the influence of the process of the experiment.	No (partial or complete) hypotheses, assumption or prediction evolved around the process that will be executed.	I assume that using the this solution in the calibration as it is, will create inaccuracy in our calibration
5.4 Inaccuracy and sources of bias for the process - explanation	P_A	The talks is concerned with explaining the sources of inaccuracy in the conduct of data collection process and this is beyond the process evaluation code 5.2 in the sense that this includes the explanation of how execution a step in a specific way is affecting the overall accuracy (before seeing the data but during the data collection).	When students discuss how a certain conduct may jeopardize the quality of the data without seeing the final data. This takes place during the process of data collection and is focused on explaining the effect of such conduct.	The talk is not concerned with explaining how a certain conduct jeopardize the quality and accuracy of the data prior to obtaining the final data.	The fact that we didn't make the blank calibration every time before the measurement caused our values to be off the expected range
5.5 Tactical decisions regarding the execution of the experiment	P_C	Statements that are related to tactical decisions regarding the repeating a step/series of steps. To defer from code 4.5 here it is not driven by the value that caused the discussion but due to assurance of accuracy of the measurement and time efficiency, even before they obtained the data. This usually	The talk is concerned with the actual steps for assurance of accuracy, proper and efficient data collection process and includes instruction and cautious assurances measures for insuring the accuracy and quality of data.	The talk does not include actual steps that are needed to insure higher accuracy, quality and efficiency for the data collection process.	We need to do this step now to save time If we wash the tool every time now we will get better results We need to make the blank measurement every time now before we measure our sample

		happen during the process of data collection and before obtaining the data and reflecting on them			
5.6 Process - other	P_O	Refers to a process/operation but is not related to the experiment.	Mention an operation but in a different context that the experiment at hand.	Not related to an operation.	I just hate/love titration Titration is like a torture/fantasy

Main category 6: Administration and organization

Sub category (specific topic)	Code Label	Definition	When to use the code	When NOT to use the code and <i>Alternative codes</i>	Examples of where the code applies
6.1 Organization and administration of the in-lab work (the experiment)	OA	The conversation is about organizing the working task such us dividing tasks between partners.	The talk is concerned with team work organization and division of /working together on tasks.	The concern is not for organizational aspects.	You do this part and I do this Should I clean the equipment? Can I start writing here Did you record this? Did you finish this? Come help me here.

Main category 7: Final report - *Explicitly* referring to the final report

Sub category (specific topic)	Code Label	Definition	When to use the code	When NOT to use the code and <i>Alternative codes</i>	Examples of where the code applies
7.1.1 Presenting/discussing general chemical theoretical content	FR_CC_G	The talk refers to including or excluding information related to chemical terms and content in the final report and on what and how to present it in the final report.	The discussion refers to (not) mentioning/writing aspects related to code 1.1.in the final report and how to present them.	If the CU in not concerned with theoretical content that will be part of the final report. <i>However</i> , if the talk is about administration of the who writes this part in the final report then the code “7.6.1 Organization and administration of the final report” should be considered.	We should explain this mechanism in the final report
7.1.2 Presenting/discussing specific chemical theoretical content	FR_CC_T		The discussion refers to (not) mentioning/writing aspects related to code 1.2.in the final report and how to present them.		
7.1.3 Presenting/discussing hypothesis and theoretical models	FR_CC_H		The discussion refers to (not) mentioning/writing aspects related to code 1.3.in the final report and how to present them.		

7.2.1 mentioning the equipment	FR_ES_I	The talk refers to including or excluding the types of equipment and materials they worked with in the final report and on what and how to present it in the final report.	The discussion refers to (not) mentioning/writing aspects related to code 2.1.in the final report and how to present them.	If the CU in not concerned with writing about the tools and materials in the final report. <i>However</i> , if the talk is about administration of the who writes this part in the final report then the code “7.6.1 Organization and administration of the final report” should be considered.	We need to specify which tools we used
7.2.2 Presenting/discussing way of operating the equipment	FR_ES_C		The discussion refers to (not) mentioning/writing aspects related to code 2.2.in the final report and how to present them.		
7.2.3 Presenting/discussing hypothesis and predictions about the equipment	FR_ES_H		The discussion refers to (not) mentioning/writing aspects related to code 2.3.in the final report and how to present them.		
7.3.1 mentioning the steps of operating digital devices/computers/software	FR_CD_I	The talk refers to including or excluding information related to the digital devices/computers/software they used is the final report and on what and how to present it in the final report.	The discussion refers to (not) mentioning/writing aspects related to code 3.1.in the final report and how to present them.	If the CU in not concerned with the digital hardware/software they used that will be part of the final report. <i>However</i> , if the talk is about administration of the who writes this part in the final report then the code “7.6.1 Organization and administration of the final report” should be considered.	We should give some background about this device in the final report we can talk about other software that we could use in the final report
7.3.2 discussing/presenting configurations related to operating the digital devices/computers/software	FR_CD_C		The discussion refers to (not) mentioning/writing aspects related to code 3.2.in the final report and how to present them.		
7.3.3 discussing/presenting Hypothesis/predictions related to the digital devices/computers/software	FR_CD_H		The discussion refers to (not) mentioning/writing aspects related to code 3.3.in the final report and how to present them.		
7.4.1 Presenting/discussing the values and data	FR_D_I	The talk refers to including or excluding information, analysis of, interpretation of and all of what is related to the data (values) they obtained that is part of the final report and on what and how to present it in the final report.	The discussion refers to (not) mentioning/writing aspects related to code 4.1.in the final report and how to present them.	If the CU in not concerned with data about all related aspects of data analysis and presentation that will be part of the final report. <i>However</i> , if the talk is about administration of the who writes this part in the final report then the code “7.6.1 Organization and administration of the final report” should be considered.	The calculation of errors should be writing like this in the final report
7.4.2 Presenting/discussing the evaluation and data analysis	FR_D_E		The discussion refers to (not) mentioning/writing aspects related to code 4.2.in the final report and how to present them.		
7.4.3 Presenting/discussing predictions and hypothesis	FR_D_H		The discussion refers to (not) mentioning/writing aspects related to code 4.3 in the final report and how to present them.		

7.5.1.1 Presenting/discussing procedures	FR_P_I_S	The talk refers to including or excluding information related to procedures they executed in the final report and on what and how to present it.	The discussion refers to (not) mentioning/writing aspects related to code 5.1.1.in the final report and how to present them (such as coping parts from the script).	If the CU in not concerned with procedures they executed that will be part of the final report. <i>However</i> , if the talk is about administration of the who writes this part in the final report then the code “7.6.1 Organization and administration of the final report” should be considered.	We need to elaborate on the steps we followed and how we did them
7.5.1.2 restating the steps they followed	FR_P_I		The discussion refers to (not) mentioning/writing aspects related to code 5.1.2.in the final report and how to present them.		
7.5.2.1 presenting explanations on how they carried out a step/procedure	FR_P_D		The discussion refers to (not) mentioning/writing aspects related to code 5.2.1.in the final report and how to present them.		
7.5.2.2 presenting/discussing reasoning related to the steps they followed and why	FR_P_E		The discussion refers to (not) mentioning/writing aspects related to code 5.2.2.in the final report and how to present them (such as reasoning of why they did this step).		
7.5.3 presenting/discussing predictions and hypotheses regarding the procedure	FR_P_H		The discussion refers to (not) mentioning/writing aspects related to code 5.3.in the final report and how to present them.		
7.6.1 Organization and administration of the final report	FR_OA	The talk refers to administrating, organizing or dividing the work load of the final report.	The discussion refers to how will the report be written (who writes what), when, and other logistics of the actual preparation of the final report.	If the CU in not concerned with administrating, organizing or dividing the work load of the final report.	You do this part, I do that
7.7 Final report - Other	FR_O	The talk is about the final report but in none of the above subcategories.	The CU is about the final report but in none of the above subcategories.	The CU in not related to the final report in any way.	That is going to be a very hard report

Main Category 8: Short answers

Sub category (specific topic)	Code Label	Definition	When to use the code	When NOT to use the code and <i>Alternative codes</i>	Examples of where the code applies
8.1.1 Short answer following code 1.1	SA_CC_G	Sentence that does not yield a contextual meaning on its own, meaning that it is not possible to detect a meaningful content in	The CU is a short answer following code 1.1.	When this CU in not a short answer.	Yes, no, I don't know, Aha That was helpful. Got it I will
8.1.2 Short answer following code 1.2	SA_CC_T		The CU is a short answer following code 1.2.		

8.1.3 Short answer following code 1.3	SA_CC_H	this CU. This CU is not part of another CU. For this category, when short answer is detected, there needs to be an examination of the coding of the previous CU and based on this to code the short answer.	The CU is a short answer following code 1.3.		I did
8.2.1 Short answer following 2.1	SA_ES_I		The CU is a short answer following code 2.1.		
8.2.2 Short answer following 2.2	SA_ES_C		The CU is a short answer following code 2.2.		
8.2.3 Short answer following 2.3	SA_ES_H		The CU is a short answer following code 2.3.		
8.3.1 Short answer following code 3.1	SA_CD_I		The CU is a short answer following code 3.1.		
8.3.2 Short answer following code 3.2	SA_CD_C		The CU is a short answer following code 3.2.		
8.3.3 Short answer following code 3.3	SA_CD_H		The CU is a short answer following code 3.3.		
8.4.1 Short answer following code 4.1	SA_D_I		The CU is a short answer following code 4.1.		
8.4.2 Short answer following code 4.2	SA_D_E		The CU is a short answer following code 4.2.		
8.4.3 Short answer following code 4.3	SA_D_H		The CU is a short answer following code 4.3.		
8.5.1.1 Short answer following code 5.1.1	SA_P_I_S		The CU is a short answer following code 5.1.1.		
8.5.1.2 Short answer following code 5.1.2	SA_P_I		The CU is a short answer following code 5.1.2.		
8.5.2.1 Short answer following code 5.2.1	SA_P_D		The CU is a short answer following code 5.2.1.		
8.5.2.2 Short answer following code 5.2.2	SA_P_E		The CU is a short answer following code 5.2.2.		
8.5.3 Short answer following code 5.3	SA_P_H		The CU is a short answer following code 5.3.		
8.6 Short answers following code 6.1	SA_OA		The CU is a short answer following code 6.1.		
8.7 Short answer following any code in category 7	SA_FR		This is a short answer that followed a statement that was coded in category 7.		
8.8 following instructors statement	SA_I		This is a short answer that followed a statement that was coded in category 9.		

Main Category 9: Instruction

Sub category (specific topic)	Code Label	Definition	When to use the code	When NOT to use the code and <i>Alternative codes</i>	Examples of where the code applies
9.1 Teaching staff instruction about Chemical terms and content	I_CC	When the speaker is the laboratory assistant, lab supervisor or any other teaching staff (TS). Then the content of the CU should be coded according to the main concern of the statement.	The TS is talking about chemical theoretical content	The TS is not talking about chemical theoretical content	Iodine reacts with Catalysis work like this...
9.2 Teaching staff instruction about Laboratory equipment, substances and tools	I_ES		The TS is talking about Laboratory equipment, substances and tools.	The TS is not talking about Laboratory equipment, substances and tools.	Using this pipit for taking the sample might/will.... Don't use this solution. Don't you see that the color is odd?
9.3 Teaching staff instruction about Computers and digital devices	I_CD		The TS is talking about the computers, software and digital devices that should be used.	The TS is not talking about the computers, software and digital devices that should be used.	This device/software works like this....
9.4 Teaching staff instruction about Data	I_D		The TS is talking about data and values.	The TS is not talking about data and values.	The number 5 is far from the expected values You should retake the measurement (to get another value)
9.5 Teaching staff instruction about Procedure	I_P		The TS is talking about the processes executed and the steps followed.	The TS is not talking about the processes executed and the steps followed.	Did you do the bulk measurement? Did you insure that the time from mixing the substances till making the measurement didn't exceed 2 minutes
9.6 Teaching staff instruction about Administration and organization	I_O		The TS is talking about the team work, and organization of the workload between students and how the work should, generally, be done in Laboratory settings. Including general safety measures, ethics, etc.	The TS is not talking about the team work, and organization of the workload between students and how the work should be done in Laboratory settings and is not concerned with general safety measures.	You booth should be working together/apart/in this way This substance should be discarded only in this bin Wear your protective glasses
9.7 Teaching staff instruction about presenting information in the Final report	I_FR		The TS is talking about information that should be mentioned, explained and/or discussed in the final report.	The TS in not talking about aspects of the Final report.	This should be discussed in the final report
9.8 short answer from the teaching staff	I_SA		Short answers provided by the teaching staff, usually following students questions or comments	The TS is stating a short answer	The TS is not stating short answer, rather they are providing statements that can be

				coded with the other codes in category 9	
9.9 Teaching staff instruction -Other	I_O	The speaker is TS but the main concern is not the above topics in this category.	The TS is talking, but not about the above topics.	The TS is not the speaker.	The weather is nice today Happy birthday You look worried today

Main category 10: Requesting support from and consulting TS

Sub category (specific topic)	Code Label	Definition	When to use the code	When NOT to use the code and <i>Alternative codes</i>	Examples of where the code applies
10.1 Requesting support from and/or consulting TS on Chemical terms and content		To clarify/discuss the issues related to chemical terms and content.	When TP addresses the TS to consult the corresponding topic.	When they are not addressing TS.	asking to see them or when they will come, they are not here, they are at lunch
10.2 Requesting support from and/or consulting TS on laboratory equipment, substances and tools		To clarify/discuss the issues related to laboratory equipment, substances and tools			
10.3 Requesting support from and/or consulting TS on computers and digital devices		To clarify/discuss the issues related to computers and digital devices.			
10.4 Requesting support from and/or consulting TS on data		To clarify/discuss the issues related to data.			
10.5 Requesting support from and/or consulting TS on process		To clarify/discuss the issues related to the process they do throughout the experiment.			
10.6 Requesting support from and/or consulting TS on administration and organisation		To clarify/discuss the issues related to the administration and organisation.			
10.7 Requesting support from and/or consulting TS on the final report		To clarify/discuss the issues related to the final report.			
10.8 Requesting support from and/or consulting TS on instruction		To clarify/discuss the issues related to the instruction.			

10.9 Requesting support from and/or consulting TS on other topics		To clarify/discuss the issues related to other topics.			
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Main category 11: Other

Sub category (specific topic)	Code Label	Definition	When to use the code	When NOT to use the code and <i>Alternative codes</i>	Examples of where the code applies
11.1 Other	X	Does not fit into the other categories.	The CU does not fit into the other categories.		The teaching staff was annoying What are you having for lunch I feel so tired today

Part II – The Critical Thinking Skills Profile (CTSP) - Determining the CT subskills that are applied inside the laboratory

1. Introduction

1.1. The aim:

This coding manual aims at determining the main Critical Thinking (CT) subskill that is applied within each relevant Coding Unit (CU)

1.2. Definition of CT - The conceptualization of CT and its interrelated skills and abilities

CT is one among a family of closely related forms of higher-order thinking skills, along with, for example, problem-solving, decision-making, and creative thinking.

Forty-six experts on CT published the APA Delphi report (1990) as a consensus for the definition of CT and its subskills. According to this report, CT is an essential tool of inquiry. It is defined as a “...purposeful, self-regulatory judgment which results in interpretation, analysis, evaluation, and inference, as well as explanation of the evidential, conceptual, methodological, criteriological, or contextual considerations upon which that judgment is based.” pp. 3. It is important to note that CT is operated in two dimensions: cognitive skills and affective dispositions. The APA report explains that “The ideal critical thinker is habitually inquisitive, well-informed, trustful of reason, open-minded, flexible, fair-minded in evaluation, honest in facing personal biases, prudent in making judgments, willing to reconsider, clear about issues, orderly in complex matters, diligent in seeking relevant information, reasonable in the selection of criteria, focused in inquiry, and persistent in seeking results which are as precise as the subject and the circumstances of inquiry permit.” Pp. 3. The report emphasizes that Good critical thinkers use the abovementioned cognitive skills and nurture those dispositions that consistently yield useful insights and judgments.

Although a critical thinker applies cognitive skills and affective dispositions, this coding manual aims to determine the cognitive skills used together with self-regulation and self-correction.

The coding manual uses the APA Delphi report’s conceptualization of CT as guidance for CT skills determination.

CT, by definition, is a process that involves the use of a set of various skills and abilities. Although the report groups and classifies those CT skills for assessment and instruction, these actions do not intend to indicate or imply that this set of skills is separate and mutually exclusive. For instance, in practical contexts, some skills and subskills **presuppose** others (further explanation will be presented in section 1.4).

Working definition of CT: CT is a reasonable reflective thinking focused on deciding what to believe or do (Ennis, 1985 & 2015)

1.3. Where it applies – forms of application

This coding manual will be used to produce transcripts of the talk given by participants inside the laboratory. This coding manual can be used in two ways:

1. On its own – to determine the CT subskills
2. Together with a precoding system to determine the CT subskills and context.

1.3.1. Using the CTSP coding manual on its own

The CU's definition and operational aspects must be followed independently.

If the statement has a sentence or question structure, then the CU ends after the meaning of the unit is determined. CU has a distinct meaning; hence, an entity of meaning is described when the statement has a distinct and independent meaning for understanding the transcript's context. The statement can be composed of one or up to as many words as needed to present a unit with independent and distinct meaning. This means that the CU ends if, and only if, a new main or subordinate clause starts, which has no reference to the previous clause to understand the meaning of the clause. Consequently, the statements **should be broken down into individual CU** when each CU forms an independent context of meaning.

Example 1.3.1.1: "We need to mix the acid with the base." – This is a statement that forms an entity of meaning on its own, and therefore, **one CU**.

Example 1.3.1.2: "wash the tools and in the meanwhile I am working on the calibration phase." – This statement has **two CUs** with two independent meanings:
CU 1: "Wash the tools."
CU 2: "In the meantime, I am working on the calibration phase."

Example 1.3.1.3: "Do you think our sample is contaminated and we need to make another one?" - This whole statement is **one CU**, since the second main clause "we need to make another one" cannot be understood without the first main clause.

Some statements that form an independent unit do not form a clear meaning; however, it was a **follow-up** on the previous talk. To determine the meaning, the coder has to review *one or more CUs up and/or down* until the context is understood.

Example 1.3.1.4: “Does this make sense?” – The word “this” has to be understood to determine what this statement refers to. If no supporting information, mentioned in [], is available, then reviewing one *CU up and/or down* is needed for this clarification.

Some statements are a response to the previous talk. If the statements are a relatively **short answer/response** to the previous talk, this coding manual is considered a CU.

Example 1.3.1.5: “Aha, I understand” – this is one CU responding to a previous CU.

Example 1.3.1.6: “Ok, I will do that” – This CU responds to a previous statement.

So far, we have reviewed several examples and cases of CU that form entities of meaning. However, not all units/statements in the transcripts form an entity of meaning, for they were, for instance, interrupted, lacking clarity due to audio technicalities, or simply because the speaker did not complete the phrase.

Due to the limitations of the devices used to record the speech and to capture students’ activities in the laboratory, the meaning of some statements of the CU cannot be determined. The reasons could include static noises, students being further away from the audio/video device, background noises, etc. In such cases, the CU is considered **inaudible**.

Example 1.3.1.7: “I think that I should.....” [Transcript stops here] – There is no clear idea of the purpose of this sentence since it was incomplete.

Example 1.3.1.8: “You should put [noise]” – there were technical issues with the audio records, and the rest of the sentence was not recorded or could not be transcribed

Example 1.3.1.9: “I will start with [high background noises]”. This statement was on a specific topic, yet the issue here was the quality of the audio recording. The topic of the statement could not be determined due to audio issues.

Due to the nature of the working environment in the laboratory, working with others, and due to the nature of oral speech, some statements might be interrupted and not completed to form an independent meaning. If the next CU is a continuation of the interrupted CU, then both parts will be considered one CU – even if the speaker was a different person.

Example 1.3.1.10: Stu1: “I will do, uhmmm, ...”
 Stu2: “The calibration” – both statements for one CU.

If the statement was interrupted and the following CU (one CU down) does not complete the interrupted CU, then in this case, the interrupted statement will be considered as an *interrupted speech*.

Example 1.3.1.11: “Did you know that [Student was interrupted by the laboratory assistant]. In this example, the statement was not completed due to an interruption of speech.

1.3.2. Using the CTSP coding manual together with the precoding system, the CP

If used with the pre-coding system in Part I, the CP, to determine the CT subskill and its context, then first use the CP part of the coding manual as a pre-coding on a given transcript. This pre-coding determines:

- The CU
- Indicates who the speaker is in each CU
- Specifies the main topic of the CU (the context).

Relying on this pre-coding system has three benefits:

1. No statement in the transcript will be left uncoded.
2. Instead of going through the whole transcript for detecting CT subskills, the primary coding (the pre-coding) screens out statements that do not apply skills related to CT, for example, “the color of this liquid is nice” or “where is the Erlenmeyer”. This way, only CUs with higher-order thinking and those related to CT are treated in this coding manual.
3. Contextualized coding for CT skills. For each statement, the context in which the skill was applied will be known, and also the speaker will be identified.

The added value of using this coding manual with the precoding system will allow a better analysis and understanding of CT in a laboratory setting.

After finishing coding with the precoding system, the CP treats the CU that are relevant to CT with this coding manual (as explained in the following section)

1.3.2.1. The CU that the CP precoding system will address

One of the purposes of the pre-coding system, the CP, is to eliminate the simplistic and less relevant statements to the experiment at hand, inside the laboratory, and to CT. For example, in the main category 1 of the CP – “Chemical terms and content”, the sub-code 1.1 “General chemistry”, is by definition “The TP mentions, explains or asks about chemical terms, principles and general methods, or the alike, but **not related** to the experiment at hand”, therefore, it is excluded from coding with this CT coding manual. Also, in the same main category, sub-code 1.5 “Theoretical Chemistry – others”, is not specific enough for the further coding of CT. The remaining subcodes from main category 1 are 1.2-1.4 (see table 1.3.2.1 below). A similar explanation applies to main categories 4-5, since they follow a similar structure to main category 1. Main categories 2 “Laboratory equipment, substances and tools” and 3 “Computers and digital devices” are mostly technical and related to using and manoeuvring tools and equipment, therefore only subcodes 2.3 and 3.3, both called “Predicting outcomes and Generating Hypotheses” (but each in its different context). In addition, some main categories were excluded from this coding manual for several reasons. For instance, the main category 7 “Final report” mostly refers to “who is writing what” in the final report and is mostly an organizational talk. Main category 8 is “short answers” that are statements that do not yield a meaning on their own. Main category 9 “Instruction” concerns statements that the instructors speak and not the students; however, in this study, CT focuses on the learner side of the story and not the instructor. Therefore, categories 7, 8, 9, and 0 (the un-codable CU) were excluded from the CTSP coding.

The remaining categories and their subcodes that are to be addressed in this coding manual are listed in the following table.

Table 1.3.2.1 – The subcodes from the pre-coding system (CP) that the CTSP coding manual should address

Number and name of main category	Code #	Name of code
1. Chemical terms and content	1.2	Background & Theoretical Chemistry
	1.3	Predicting outcomes and Generating hypotheses
	1.4	Generating chemical explanation or expectation – post hoc
	1.5	Theoretical Chemistry - Other
2. Laboratory equipment, substances and tools (Non-digital Equipment and tools)	2.2	Configuring the Equipment
	2.3	Predicting outcomes and Generating Hypotheses
	2.4	Equipment - other
3. Computers and digital devices (Devices and software oriented)	3.3	Predicting outcomes and Generating hypotheses
4. Data (Value oriented)	4.2	Evaluating data (cognitive and metacognitive)
	4.3	Predicting outcomes and Generating hypotheses – prior to execution
	4.4.1-4.4.8	Interpretation, predictions and analysis of data - post hoc (with and without supporting information)
	4.5	Conclusions and next steps (tactical decisions)
	4.6	Data - Others
5. Procedure (process oriented)	5.2.1	Process Demonstration and instruction
	5.2.2	Process Evaluating (cognitive and metacognitive)
	5.3	Predicting outcome and Generating hypotheses
	5.4	Inaccuracy and sources of bias for the process - explanation
	5.5	Tactical decisions regarding the execution of the experiment
	5.6	Process - Others

6. Administration and organization	6.1	Administration and organization
10. Requesting support from and consulting TS	10.1-10.9	Requesting support from and/or consulting TS on various topics
11. Others	11	Off topic talk that is spoken during sessions

1.4. Overview of the skills, interconnections, and progressive coding

This coding manual will allow a unique format for coding - Progressive Coding. Before explaining progressive coding, there is a need to have an overall understanding of the CT subskills and their interconnections.

1.4.1. Overview of the skills and their interconnections

Important notice: According to the APA Delphi report (1990), CT involves using various skills and abilities that are grouped and classified into six main skills. However, the report indicates that these six main skills and their subskills are not mutually exclusive (Facione, 1990). The illustrated potential relationships between the main skills in this section have not been presented in the literature so far. This section aims to outline this potential relationship and ease the user of this manual. Nevertheless, the arrows and descriptions below do not imply that the process of CT happens in linear steps and a specific order. One can use several skills and move back and forth between the skills. This illustration, however, shows a potential relationship of presupposition and is in line with the definitions of CT (see Ennis, 1985 and 2015).

This coding manual is composed of 6 main skills, and each skill translates into several subskills. In some main skills and their subskills, the further down you go with the subskills, the level of thinking increases, and the skill advances. We further grouped these six categories into two overarching groups – “CT processing skills” (CTSP_1.1-1.3) and “CT outcome skills” (CTSP_2.1-2.3) (Fig.3) – following Ennis’s (1985, 2015) dual focus and distinction between process, “reasonable reflective thinking” and outcomes, “deciding what to believe or do”. Figure 1.4.1 presents the CT processing skills and CT outcomes skills.

Figure 1.4.1 – CTSP – CT processing skills and CT outcomes skills

Part II – CTSP – CT skills and subskills

1_CT Processing - Main categories of codes:

- 1.1_ Interpretation– clarifying meaning
- 1.2_ Analysis–examining arguments
- 1.3_ Evaluation–assigning value to claims

2_CT Outcomes – Main categories of codes:

- 2.1_ Actions and Inference – Deciding on an action and Inference by drawing conclusions
- 2.2_ Self/Group -regulation, -examination, and -correction – Employing and reacting to fallacy labels
- 2.3_ Explanation – presenting positions or arguments orally or in writing

3_Others

Also, in some skills and subskills, there is a relationship of presupposition. Figure 1.4.2 presents an overview of the potential relationships between the main skills.

Figure 1.4.2 - Overview of the relationships between the main skills

In other words, skills 1.1-1.3 build on each other, and the previous is a presupposition for the next. Main skill 1.1 “Interpretation – Clarifying meaning” is focused on comprehending and expressing the meaning, and main skill 1.2 “Analysis – Examining Ideas” is focused on identifying the intended and actual inferential relationships among statements. Skill 2.2 can be an overarching skill at any process step. Skill 2.3 is forming the final decision regarding the “what to believe or do” from the definition of CT.

When it comes to subskills, some skills build on the previous, but mostly, the subskills within each main skill are independent of other subskills.

For this coding manual, there is a need to **first** understand the purpose of the CU to determine the skill's main category, **then** assign the most relevant sub-code.

1.4.2. Progressive coding

Progressive coding (PC), a term from the digital graphics domain, means that given one data set, the next data set will build on the first and add more resolution and complexity. Since it is suggested in the literature that the CT skills are not mutually exclusive and have some interconnections, and based on the interconnections outlined in section 1.4, consider the highest skill that is applicable when a CU seems to fit into one of the main 1-5 skills.

Summary of section 1.4:

- ✓ The purpose of the CU will determine the most relevant main skill (1.1-2.3)
- ✓ If one of the main skills 1-5 seems suitable, consider the highest applicable skill
- ✓ When the main skill is determined, assign the sub-code (subskill)
- ✓ If the CU is a question, use the code that ends with Q (ex., 1.1.Q), and if it's a statement, use the codes that end with S (1.1.S)
- ✓ Any CU that fits into none of the main skills 1.1-2.3 will receive the code 3

1.5. How to code

Guidance for coding:

- ✓ The purpose of the CU will determine the most relevant main skill (1.1-2.3) – You can better determine the purpose by asking the question “what was this CU stated for? What was the purpose?”
- ✓ Consider the highest applicable skill if one of the main skills 1.1-2.3 seems suitable.
- ✓ When the main skill is determined, assign the sub-code (subskill)
- ✓ If the CU is a question, use the code that ends with Q (ex., 1.1.Q), and if it’s a statement, use the codes that end with S (1.1.S)
- ✓ Any CU that fits into none of the main skills 1.1-2.3 will receive the code 3

Example:

CU#	Speaker	Topic	CT subskill
20	St1	4.4.3	1.2.S
....			
24	St1	5.4	2.3.Q

2. The Codes of CTSP – Main Categories, sub-codes, definition and examples

Main Category 0: CU with incomplete meaning (to be used if this coding manual is ***used independently*** – without the precoding system. If used with the pre-coding system, skip to the next categories 1-3 below.

Sub category (specific topic)		Code Label	Definition	When to use the code	When NOT to use the code and <i>Alternative codes</i>	Examples of where the code applies
0.2 Interrupted speech	0.1.1 Interrupted speech – spoken by a student	BS_S	Sentence / part of a sentence that does not yield a meaning. The sentence is incomplete. For example, it was interrupted by another person, event or that the speaker has stopped speaking for an evident or unevident reason	The speaker is a student and the CU is an incomplete statement	The CU has a meaningful context and topic is conceivable	I think that I should..... [transcripts stops here] The problem here is that..... [transcripts stops here]
	0.1.2 Interrupted speech - spoken by a TS	BS_I		The speaker is a TS and the CU is an incomplete statement		

Sub category (specific topic)		Code Label	Definition	When to use the code	When NOT to use the code and <i>Alternative codes</i>	Examples of where the code applies
0.2. Inaudible	0.2.1 Inaudible content - spoken by a student	UC_S	Content is undetectable due to audio issues. Usually, the transcript indicates missing information that is due to audio issues (such as scratching or noises that did not enable full transcription of the statement). Occurrence of audio issues prevents the determination of the topic of the CU.	The speaker is a student and the CU is missing information due to audio issues	The CU has a meaningful context [noise] [inaudible]
	0.2.2 Inaudible content - spoken by TS	UC_I		The speaker is an instructor and the CU is missing information due to audio issues		

Main Categories 1.1-2.3: CT skills

Reference:

Main categories 1.1-2.3:

Facione, P. (1990). Critical thinking: A statement of expert consensus for purposes of educational assessment and instruction (The Delphi Report).

Peter A. Facione, principal investigator, The California Academic Press, Millbrae, CA, 1990. (ERIC ED 315 423)

Facione, P. A. (2015). Critical thinking: What it is and why it counts. *Insight assessment, 2019*, 1-30.

Butterworth, J., & Thwaites, G. (2013). *Thinking skills: critical thinking and problem solving*. Cambridge University Press.

Main category 2.1-2.3:

Ennis, R. H. (1985). A logical basis for measuring critical thinking skills. *Educational leadership, 43*(2), 44-48.

Ennis, R. H. (2015). Critical Thinking: A Streamlined Conception. In Davies, M., & Barnett, R. (Eds.). (2015). *The Palgrave handbook of critical thinking in higher education*. Springer. 31-48

Butterworth, J., & Thwaites, G. (2013). *Thinking skills: critical thinking and problem solving*. Cambridge University Press.

	Main category – Constructs and purpose	subskills	Code	Operational definition of the subskill (Modified to fit the context)	Examples specific to working inside a laboratory (* examples from Facione, 1990, ** examples from Facione, 2015 – wording might apply to allow examples to fit into the Laboratory settings)
1. CT Processing skills	1.1 Interpretation– clarifying meaning Purpose: “To comprehend and express the meaning or significance of a wide variety of experiences, situations, data, events, judgments, conventions, beliefs, rules, procedures or criteria” (Facione, 1990, pp. 13)	Categorization (Facione, 1990, pp. 13)	1.1.1.S	The CU is a statement that refers to creating “comprehensible meaning” by “[formulating] categories, distinctions, or frameworks for understanding, describing or characterizing information” (Facione, 1990, pp. 13)	To determine a useful way of sorting and sub-classifying information * To make an understandable report of what one experienced in a given situation* To classify data, findings or opinions using a given classification schema* Oh, this belongs to ... So this is So this step is part of
			1.1.1.Q	The CU is a Question that requires creating “comprehensible meaning” by “[formulating] categories, distinctions, or frameworks for understanding, describing or characterizing information” (Facione, 1990, pp. 13)	What is the best way to characterize/categorize/classify this? ** What kind of compound is this? What is this kind of procedure?
		Decoding Significance (Facione, 1990, pp. 14)	1.1.2.S	The CU is a statement that “[attends] to, and describes the informational content, ... rules, procedures, criteria, [intentions] or inferential relationships expressed in ... language, [conversation,] ... numbers, graphs, tables, charts, ... and symbols” (Facione, 1990, pp. 14)	to interpret the data displayed or presented using a particular form of instrumentation* this number is our data this value/graph shows our max value
			1.1.2.Q	The CU is a question that requires “[describing] the informational content, ... rules, procedures, criteria,	How should we understand that? ** In this context, what was intended by saying/doing that? **

				[intentions] or inferential relationships expressed in ... language, [conversation,] ... numbers, graphs, tables, charts, ... and symbols" (Facione, 1990, pp. 14)	How can we make sense out of this (experience, feeling, or statement)?** What does this number mean? What is the significance of this number?
	Clarifying Meaning (Facione, 1990, pp. 14)	1.1.3.S		The CU is a statement that is a "paraphrase or making more explicit, through stipulation, description, analogy or figurative expression, the contextual, conventional or intended meanings of words, ideas, concepts, statements, behaviors, drawings, numbers, signs, charts, graphs, symbols, rules, [or] events ... [all for the purpose of] remov[ing] confusing, unintended vagueness or ambiguity ..." (Facione, 1990, pp. 14)	to restate what a person said using different words or expressions while preserving that person's intended meanings* To find an example which helps explain something to someone* Clarifying what a sign, chart or graph means So this number can be used to understand ...
		1.1.3.Q		The CU is a Question that requires "paraphrase[ing] or making more explicit, through stipulation, description, analogy or figurative expression, the contextual, conventional or intended meanings of words, ideas, concepts, statements, behaviors, drawings, numbers, signs, charts, graphs, symbols, rules, [or] events ... [all for the purpose of] remov[ing] confusing, unintended vagueness or ambiguity ..." (Facione, 1990, pp. 14)	Could you explain what he or she just said? Could you restate how the process here should work in your own words?
	Other	1.1.4.S		The CU is a statement that refers to "comprehend[ing] and express[ing] the meaning or significance of a wide variety of experiences, situations, data, events, judgments, conventions, beliefs, rules, procedures or criteria" (Facione, 1990, pp. 13) but fits in none of the above sub codes 1.1.S-1.3.Q	This would mean... To clarify this, I will ...
		1.1.4.Q		The CU is a question that requires "comprehend[ing] and express[ing] the meaning or significance of a wide variety of experiences, situations, data, events, judgments, conventions, beliefs, rules, procedures or criteria" (Facione, 1990, pp. 13) but fits in none of the above sub codes 1.1.S-1.3.Q	What does this mean? ** What's happening? ** Does this make sense?
	1.2 Analysis-examining arguments	Examining Ideas	1.2.1.S	The CU is a statement that is concerned either with "comparing or contrasting ideas, concepts, or statements" or with "identifying issues or problems and determine their component parts, and also to identify the conceptual relationships of those parts to each other and to the whole" (Facione, 1990, Pp. 14)	To examine closely related proposals regarding a given problem and to determine their points of similarity and/or divergence * Given a complicated assignment, to determine how it might be broken up into smaller, more manageable tasks*
	Purpose: "To identify the intended and actual inferential relationships among statements, questions, concepts, descriptions or other forms of representation intended to express beliefs, judgments,		1.2.1.Q	The CU is a question that is concerned either with "comparing or contrasting ideas, concepts, or statements" or with "identifying issues or problems and determine their component parts, and also to identify the conceptual relationships of those parts to each other and to the whole" (Facione, 1990, Pp. 14)	How would you suggest we approach this problem, how is this better/different from other approaches? How would this step contribute to our overall problem? Why is this step necessary?
		Detecting Arguments	1.2.2.S	"Given a set of statements, descriptions, questions or graphic representations," The CU is a statement that aims	It sounds like you are assuming that the fluid index is constant

	experiences, reasons, information, or opinions” (Facione, 1990, Pp. 14)			at identifying unstated assumptions OR on “determin[ing] whether or not the set expresses, or is intended to express, a reason or reasons In support of or contesting some claim, opinion or point of view” (Facione, 1990, Pp. 15), meaning, does the claim make sense in its structure?	This argument would only be true if you assume that... What you have said fits/does not fit together This piece of information is related to what you have just said
			1.2.2.Q	The CU is a question that aims at ‘determin[ing] whether or not ... a set of statements, descriptions, questions or graphic representations, ... expresses or is intended to express, a reason or reasons In support of or contesting some claim, opinion or point of view ” (Facione, 1990, Pp. 15), meaning, does the claim make sense in its structure?	What is the underlying assumption here? Does this argument seem to have adequate reasoning? What other reasons do you have? Please tell us again your reasons for making that claim** What are the arguments pro and con?*** [given a pice of information] why?
		Analyzing Arguments	1.2.3.S	The main concern of the CU is to identify the parts of the argument and recognizing how they relate to each other, especially how the reasons relate to the conclusion. This goes a step further that the previous codes 2.2.S & 2.2.Q, it brings into account unexpressed element, premises, reasons, or underlying assumptions that are necessary/relevant to capturing the intended main conclusion	What you are suggesting will not get us higher accuracy, your suggestion, in fact, reduces it Your reasons do not fit all together When given several reasons or chains of reasons in support of a particular claim, to develop a graphic representation which usefully characterizes the inferential flow of that reasoning*
			1.2.3.Q	The CU is a question that is concerned with identifying the parts of the argument and recognizing how they relate to each other, especially how the reasons relate to the conclusion. This goes a step further that the previous codes 2.2.S & 2.2.Q, it brings into account unexpressed element, premises, reasons, or underlying assumptions that are necessary/relevant to capturing the intended main conclusion	Which claim does not fit the overall argument? Does the reasons fit the conclusion? How do your explanations lead to this conclusion? What is your conclusion/What is it that you are claiming?*** What assumptions must we make to accept that conclusion?***
		Other	1.2.4.S	The CU is a statement that is related to “identify[ing] the intended and actual inferential relationships among statements, questions, concepts, descriptions or other forms of representation intended to express beliefs, judgments, experiences, reasons, information, or opinions” (Facione, 1990, pp.14), but does not fit into the above sub codes 2.1.S-2.3.Q.	His/her argument is sound/not reasonable because... (the composition and structure of the argument)
			1.2.4.Q	The CU is a question related to “identify[ing] the intended and actual inferential relationships among statements, questions, concepts, descriptions or other forms of representation intended to express beliefs, judgments, experiences, reasons, information, or opinions” (Facione, 1990, pp.14), but does not fit into the above sub codes 2.1.S-2.3.Q.	Explain how strong/weak is his/her argument (the composition and structure of argument)?
	1.3 Evaluation-assigning value to claims	ASSESSING CLAIMS	1.3.1.S	The CU is a statement that is concerned with either: 1) assessing a claim by “assess[ing] the contextual relevance of questions, information, principles, rules or procedural	To determine the credibility of a source of information to recognize the factors which make a person credible regarding a given event or on a given topic

<p>Purpose: "To assess the credibility of statements or other representations which are accounts or descriptions of a person's perception, experience, situation, judgment, belief, or opinion; and to assess the logical strength of the actual or intend inferential relationships among statements, descriptions, questions or other forms of representation" (Facione, 1990, pp.15)</p>	<p>Assess credibility of claims</p>		<p>directions", or 2) "assessing the degree of credibility to ascribe to a source of information or opinion". And overall, "to assess the acceptability, the level of confidence, to place in the probability or truth of any given representation of an experience, situation, judgment, belief or opinion" (Facione, 1990, pp.15)</p>	<p>To determine if a given principle of conduct is applicable to deciding what to do in a given situation To determine if a given claim is likely to be true or false based on what one knows or can reasonably find out This is a false report because...</p>
		1.3.1.Q	<p>The CU is a question concerned with either: 1) assessing a claim by "assess[ing] the contextual relevance of questions, information, principles, rules or procedural directions", or 2) "assessing the degree of credibility to ascribe to a source of information or opinion". And overall, "to assess the acceptability, the level of confidence, to place in the probability or truth of any given representation of an experience, situation, judgment, belief or opinion" (Facione, 1990, pp.15)</p>	<p>Why do you trust what he says? Do you trust his information? Based on what? Are you sure this is the right principle to apply in this situation? Does this seem to convey our data in the right way? How credible is that claim?***</p>
	ASSESSING ARGUMENTS Assess quality of arguments that were made using inductive or deductive reasoning	1.3.2.S	<p>The CU is a statement that is concerned with "judg[ing] whether the assumed acceptability of the premises of a given argument justify one's accepting as true (deductively certain), or very probably true (inductively justified), the expressed conclusion of that argument". In other words, the CU "raise[s] questions or objections", ... and to assess/evaluate whether the argument (being evaluated) "relies on false or doubtful assumptions or presuppositions and then to determine [how crucially] these affect its strength" and "... determine the extent to which possible additional information might strengthen or weaken an argument" (Facione, 1990, pp. 16)</p>	<p>Given an argument, to judge if its conclusion follows either with certainty or with a high level of confidence from its premise* Given an objection to an argument to evaluate the force of that objection* To judge the logical strength of arguments based or hypothetical situations or causal reasoning* to judge if a given argument is relevant or applicable or has implications for the situation at hand* To determine how possible new data might lead logically to the further confirmation or disconfirmation of a given principle* To compare the strengths and weaknesses of alternative interpretations To judge if several statements contradict each other, or judging if the evidence at hand supports the conclusion being drawn What he/she said raises a big question about the correctness of what we are doing, given that.... This is useful.</p>
		1.3.2.Q	<p>The CU is a question concerned with "judg[ing] whether the assumed acceptability of the premises of a given argument justify one's accepting as true (deductively certain), or very probably true (inductively justified), the expressed conclusion of that argument". In other words, the CU "raise[s] questions or objections", ... and to assess/evaluate whether the argument (being evaluated) "relies on false or doubtful assumptions or presuppositions and then to determine [how crucially] these affect its strength" and "... determine the extent to which possible additional</p>	<p>How do you evaluate this argument? How strong/weak is this argument?*** Would this argument have implication on the situation? What might be missing to increase the validity of this claim? Do you find that the claims and conclusions support each other? How confident can we be in our conclusion, given what we now know?*** Do we have our facts right?***</p>

				information might strengthen or weaken an argument” (Facione, 1990, pp. 16)	
		Other	1.3.3.S	The CU is a statement that is concerned with “assess[ing] the credibility of statements or other representations which are accounts or descriptions of a person's perception, experience, situation, judgment, belief, or opinion; and to assess the logical strength of the actual or intend inferential relationships among statements, descriptions, questions or other forms of representation” (Facione, 1990, pp. 15) but does not fit into the above sub code 3.1.S-3.2.Q	
			1.3.3.Q	The CU is a question concerned with “assess[ing] the credibility of statements or other representations which are accounts or descriptions of a person's perception, experience, situation, judgment, belief, or opinion; and to assess the logical strength of the actual or intend inferential relationships among statements, descriptions, questions or other forms of representation” (Facione, 1990, pp. 15) but does not fit into the above sub code 3.1.S-3.2.Q	
2 CT Outcomes – action, conclusion, Self-regulation/ correction and argument CT's outcome is “deciding what to believe or do” (Ennis, 1985, pp. 45), therefore a strategy or a tactical decision (Ennis, 1985) about next steps are focused on the “what to do” part of the definition And	2.1 Actions and Inference - Deciding on an action (Ennis, 1985) and Inference by drawing conclusions (Facione, 1990) – Purpose: Deciding on an activity / strategy/ tactical decision that will be made after a process of weighing possible explanations, alternatives, credibility, and/or other steps AND “to identify and secure elements needed to draw reasonable conclusions; to form conjectures and hypotheses; to	Querying Evidence	2.1.1.S	The CU is a statement that is concerned with “formulat[ing] a strategy for seeking and gathering information” (Facione, 1990, pp. 17) that is relevant and credible and necessary for supporting an argument	When attempting to develop a persuasive argument in support of one's opinion, to judge what background information it would be useful to have and to develop a plan which will yield a clear answer as to whether or not such information is available* After judging that certain missing information would be germane in determining if a given opinion is more or less reasonable than a competing opinion, to plan a search which will reveal if that information is available* If we want to achieve ... then we need to find We need to do this step now to save time We need to wash the tools every time now, so we will get better results We need to make the blank measurement every time now before we measure our sample We need to retake the first measurement because our evidence point to that our obtained data is incorrect
			2.1.1.Q	The CU is a question concerned with “formulat[ing] a strategy for seeking and gathering information” (Facione, 1990, pp. 17) that is relevant and credible and necessary for supporting an argument	What else do we need to have more accurate data and how will we do this? What additional information do we need to resolve this question?*** What can we do to save time? What can we do to increase our accuracy in the next round? Don't you see that one of our data sets is incorrect and we need to retake this measurement?

<p>self/group monitoring and correction that can be applied on other subskill throughout the process of CT is focused on the “what to believe” part of the definition. Ct outcomes includes Explanation that is justifying procedures and presenting arguments that are a result of weighting possible fallacies, validity and credibility issues, bias and other factors</p>	<p>consider relevant information and to reduce the consequences flowing from data, statements, principles, evidence, judgments, beliefs, opinions, concepts, descriptions, questions, or other forms of representation” (Facione, 1990, pp. 16)</p>	Conjecturing Alternatives	2.1.2.S	The CU is a statement that is concerned with “formulat[ing] multiple alternatives for resolving a problem” or a variety of different plans to achieve some goal (such as “to postulate a series of suppositions regarding a question, to project alternative hypotheses regarding an event”, etc.) (Facione, 1990, pp. 17)	We can do a re-measurement is the exact same way, or we can double the concentration and see if the result correlates with the equation Let’s consider each option and see where it takes us
			2.1.2.Q	The CU is a question concerned with “formulat[ing] multiple alternatives for resolving a problem” or a variety of different plans to achieve some goal (such as “to postulate a series of suppositions regarding a question, to project alternative hypotheses regarding an event”, etc.) (Facione, 1990, pp. 17)	Which possible solutions do you have for this problem? What are some alternatives we haven’t yet explored?*
		Drawing Conclusions	2.1.3.S	The CU is a statement that is mainly concerned with what can and cannot be inferred from a given information. In other words, it is concerned with “apply[ing] appropriate modes of inference in determining what position, opinion or point of view one should take on a given matter or issue” (Facione, 1990, pp. 17)	To carry out experiments and to apply appropriate statistical inference techniques in order to confirm or disconfirm an empirical hypothesis*
			2.1.3.Q	The CU is a question that is mainly concerned with what can and cannot be inferred from a given information. In other words, it is concerned with “apply[ing] appropriate modes of inference in determining what position, opinion or point of view one should take on a given matter or issue” (Facione, 1990, pp. 17)	What can we learn from these finding? Do these findings fit into the original hypothesis? Given what we know so far, what conclusions can we draw? What can we rule out?*
		Other	2.1.4.S	The CU is a statement that is concerned with “identify[ing] and securing elements needed to draw reasonable conclusions; to form conjectures and hypotheses; to consider relevant information and to reduce the consequences flowing from data, statements, principles, evidence, judgments, beliefs, opinions, concepts, descriptions, questions, or other forms of representation” (Facione, 1990, pp.16) but does not fit into any of the above sub-codes 4.1.1.S-4.1.3.Q	Based on our findings and what we understand, if we would do this experiment again but change then we would find
			2.1.4.Q	The CU is a question concerned with “identify[ing] and securing elements needed to draw reasonable conclusions; to form conjectures and hypotheses; to consider relevant information and to reduce the consequences flowing from data, statements, principles, evidence, judgments, beliefs, opinions, concepts, descriptions, questions, or other forms of representation” (Facione, 1990, pp.16) but does not fit into any of the above sub-codes 4.1.1.S-4.1.3.Q	Are there any undesirable consequences that we can and should foresee?*
	2.2 Self/grou p-regulation, -examination, and -correction - Employing and	Self-Examination	2.2.1.S	The CU is a statement that is concerned with “reflect[ing] on one’s own/group’s reasoning and verifying both the results produced and the correct application and execution of the cognitive skills involved” for the purpose of making an “objective and thoughtful meta-cognitive self/[group]-	to review one’s methodology or calculations with a view to detecting mistaken applications or in advertent errors* To reread sources to assure that one has not overlooked important information*

<p>reacting to fallacy labels – Monitoring and correcting misconceptions or fallacy labels (Ennis, 1985).</p> <p>Purpose: This category is focused on the “what to Believe” part of the definition of CT. The focus here is on accepting/rejecting understandings of a certain concept or issue (mental action) after a process of weighing possible explanations, alternatives, credibility, and/or other steps. This category is focused on “Self-consciously to monitor one’s[/group’s] cognitive activities, the elements used in those activities, and the result seduced, particularly by applying skills in analysis and evaluation to one’s own inferential judgments with a view toward questioning, confirming, validating, or correcting either one’s reasoning or one’s results” (Facione, 1990, pp. 19)</p>			assessment of [their] opinions and reasons” (Facione, 1990, pp. 19)	To identify and review one’s reasons and reasoning processes in coming to a given conclusion* I might been mistaken here, since I assumed After reviewing, I trust the process I made Monitor/reconsider an interpretation\ inference \ explanation for the purpose of examining it** Let me double check before I/we go further ** double checking by recalculating the figures** I believe you have some misunderstanding about what this concept is
		2.2.1.Q	The CU is a question concerned with “reflect[ing] on one’s own/group’s reasoning and verifying both the results produced and the correct application and execution of the cognitive skills involved” for the purpose of making an “objective and thoughtful meta-cognitive self[/group]-assessment of [their] opinions and reasons” (Facione, 1990, pp. 19)	Did you detect any fault in you conduct? Did you revive your presumptions? How good was our methodology, and how well did we follow it?*** How am I/are we doing? Have I/we missed anything important?***
	Self-Correction	2.2.2.S	“Where self-examination reveals errors or deficiencies”, the CU is focused on “design[ing] reasonable procedures to remedy or correct, if possible, those mistakes and their causes” (Facione, 1990, pp. 19)	Given a methodological mistake or factual deficiency in one’s work, to revise that work so as to correct the problem and then to determine if the revisions warrant changes in any position, findings, or opinions based thereon* Correcting an interpretation\inference \explanation for the purpose of examining it** Changing conclusion in view of the realization that one had misjudged the importance of certain factors when coming to an earlier decision** Aha, so what is meant by analytical accuracy is and not Calibration should be done in this format, and not how we made it so far
		2.2.2.Q	“Where self-examination reveals errors or deficiencies”, the CU is a question focused on “design[ing] reasonable procedures to remedy or correct, if possible, those mistakes and their causes” (Facione, 1990, pp. 19)	How would you correct this? Our position on this issue is still too vague; can we be more precise?*** I need to get this straight, what does calibration mean? I think I got this wrong, does blank measurement mean?
	Other	2.2.3.S	The CU is a statement that is focused on “Self-conscious to monitor one’s/group’s cognitive activities, the elements used in those activities, and the result seduced, particularly by applying skills in analysis and evaluation to one’s own inferential judgments with a view toward questioning, confirming, validating, or correcting either one’s reasoning or one’s results” (Facione, 1990, pp. 19) but does not fit to any of the above sub-codes 4.2.1.S-4.2.2.Q	What do we learn from our experience today is...
		2.2.3.Q	The CU is a question focused on Self-conscious to monitor one’s/group’s cognitive activities, the elements used in those activities, and the result seduced, particularly by applying skills in analysis and evaluation to one’s own inferential judgments with a view toward questioning,	I’m finding some of our definitions a little confusing; can we revisit what we mean by certain things before making any final decisions?*** How good is our evidence?*** OK, before we commit, what are we missing?***

				confirming, validating, or correcting either one's reasoning or one's results" (Facione, 1990, pp. 19) but does not fit to any of the above sub-codes 4.2.1.S-4.2.2.Q	
<p>2.3 Explanati on–presenting position or an argument orally or in writing (Ennis, 1985; Facione, 1990) –</p> <p>Purpose: “To state and to justify the results of one's reasoning; to justify that reasoning in terms of the evidential, conceptual, methodological, criteriologial and contextual considerations upon which one's results were based; and to present one's reasoning in the form of cogent arguments” (Facione, 1990, pp. 18). “Critical thinkers can explain what they think and how they arrived at that judgment” ... “This means to be able to give someone a full look at the big picture: both to state and to justify that reasoning in terms of the evidential, conceptual, methodological, criteriologial, and contextual considerations upon</p>	Stating Results describing methods and results	2.3.1.S	The CU is a statement that is concerned with “produc[ing] accurate statements, explanation, descriptions or representations of the results of one's reasoning activities so as to analyze, evaluate, infer from, or monitor those results” (Facione, 1990, pp. 18) Note: to differ this code from drawing conclusion (4.1.3.S-4.1.3.Q), “Explanation, like argument, involves giving reasons. But explanatory reasons do not lead to conclusions, as reasons do in arguments. ... Explanations tell us why something is as it is, or how it has become about” (Butterworth & Thwaites, 2013, pp. 137)	To state one's research findings* construct a chart which organizes one's findings ** to state research results and describe the methods and criteria used to achieve those results**	
		2.3.1.Q	The CU is a question concerned with “produc[ing] accurate statements, explanation, descriptions or representations of the results of one's reasoning activities so as to analyze, evaluate, infer from, or monitor those results” (Facione, 1990, pp. 18) Note: to differ this code from drawing conclusion (4.1.3.S-4.1.3.Q), “Explanation, like argument, involves giving reasons. But explanatory reasons do not lead to conclusions, as reasons do in arguments. ... Explanations tell us why something is as it is, or how it has become about” (Butterworth & Thwaites, 2013, pp. 137)	Could you present your findings? What were the specific findings/results of the investigation?***	
	Justifying Procedures	2.3.2.S	The CU is focused on “present[ing] the evidential, conceptual, methodological, criteriologial and contextual considerations which one used informing one's interpretations, analyses, evaluation or inferences, so that one might accurately record, evaluate, describe or justify those processes” (Facione, 1990, pp. 18)	To keep a log of the steps followed in working through a long or difficult problem or scientific procedure* to explain one's choice of a particular statistical test for purposes of data analysis* To state the standards one used in evaluating a piece of information* To show that the prerequisites for the use of a given technical methodology have been satisfied* To report the strategy used in attempting to make a decision in a reasonable way* to appeal to established criteria as a way of showing the reasonableness of a given judgment**	
		2.3.2.Q	The CU is a question focused on “present[ing] the evidential, conceptual, methodological, criteriologial and contextual considerations which one used informing one's interpretations, analyses, evaluation or inferences, so that one might accurately record, evaluate, describe or justify those processes” (Facione, 1990, pp. 18)	What were the exact steps that you followed? Are you sure you did all the pre-steps for this method? How did you analyze your data? What did you do? Please tell us how you conducted that analysis**	
	Presenting Arguments	2.3.3.S	This goes a step further than the codes 4.3.1.S-4.3.2.Q, this sub-code is focuses on either “giv[ing] reason for accepting some claim” or “meet[ing] objections to the method,	I would argue that the steps they performed are faulty/well-performed because...	

	which one's results were based" (Facione, 2015, pp, 6)			conceptualization, evidence, criteria or contextual appropriateness of inferential, analytical or evaluative judgments" and encounters them with an argument (Facione, 1990, pp. 18)	The findings that they presented seem to be similar/different from the finding obtained by our colleges and we think this could be due to to cite the evidence that led you to accept or reject an argument/information** You know what, I believe what we have made here makes sense, we have carried out all necessary precaution These set of data, also seem weird at first, they fit with the theory, these are constants and have therefore their influence over the data is also constant
			2.3.3.Q	This is for CU that is a question that goes beyond the codes 5.1.S-5.2.Q and focuses on "giv[ing] reason for accepting some claim" or "meet[ing] objections to the method, conceptualization, evidence, criteria or contextual appropriateness of inferential, analytical or evaluative judgments" and encounters them with an argument (Facione, 1990, pp. 18)	How would you respond to the process that was being presented? How would you think about the findings he/she just presented? Would you agree to these conclusions? How did you come to that interpretation?*** Please take us through your reasoning** So how would you think of our overall conduct? What would you conclude regarding our data set after all this day?
		Other	2.3.4.S	The CU is a statement that is concerned with "stat[ing and justifying] the results of one's reasoning; justifying that reasoning in terms of the evidential, conceptual, methodological, criteriological and contextual considerations upon which one's results were based; and presenting one's reasoning in the form of cogent arguments" (Facione, 1990, pp. 18) but does not fit to any of the above sub-codes 4.3.1.S-4.3.3.Q	
			2.3.4.Q	The CU is a question concerned with "stat[ing and justifying] the results of one's reasoning; justifying that reasoning in terms of the evidential, conceptual, methodological, criteriological and contextual considerations upon which one's results were based; and presenting one's reasoning in the form of cogent arguments" (Facione, 1990, pp. 18) but does not fit to any of the above sub-codes 4.3.1.S-4.3.3.Q	Why do you think that (was the right answer/was the solution)?*** How would you explain why this particular decision was made?***
	3. Others		3	CU that belong to the codes listed in Table 1.3.2.1 of the introduction (the pre coding system), but do not fit into any of the above main categories and their corresponding sub-codes (1.1.S-4.3.4.Q.)	

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